

ISic0537

I.Sicily inscription 0537

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Eryx

Place of origin (modern)

Erice

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Trapani, Museo Regionale

Agostino Pepoli, inventory 5227

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175710

EDR 092733

EDCS 22000842

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7257 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

- Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 284 fig.244
- Dessau, H. 1892-1916. *Inscriptiones Latinae Selectae*. Berlin. At 939
- Manganaro, G. 1987. Tacfarinas e la Sicilia (ovvero L. Apronius e il santuario ericino. In Mastino, A.(eds.), *L'Africa Romana. Atti del IV convegno di studio, Sassari, 12-14 dicembre 1986*. Sassari. pp. 581-585.
- Bivona, L. 2000. La documentazione epigrafica latina in area elima. *Atti delle terze giornate internazionali di studi sull'area elima (Gibellina, Erice, Contessa Entellina, 23-26 ottobre 1997)*. Pisa-Gibellina. pp. 153-166. At 153-154
- Campbell, J. B. 2002. War and society in imperial Rome, 31 BC-AD 284. London. At 47
- Oliveri, F. 2009. Le iscrizioni latine. In Famà, M.L.(eds.), *Il museo regionale "A. Pepoli" di Trapani. Le collezioni archeologiche*. Bari. pp. 385-396. At 389 no.1 ph

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic0537. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4384888>